

Government of National Unity in South Africa: A Shift in South Africa's Political Landscape or a Relationship of Political Parties with Mutual Survival for Relevance?

Toyin Cotties Adetiba

Department of Political and International Studies, University of Zululand, South Africa

Primarily, the formulation and implementation of social, economic, and political policies in South Africa has been built around the African National Congress, the political party that led the country to attaining its political freedom in 1994. Following the national election of 2024, where none of the party secure the absolute majority to form a government, the South African political parties have had to form the Government of National Unity with hitherto former opposition political parties. The assertion that in a divided society, the achievement of and sustainability of social, political, and economic stability through a power-sharing pact by political parties is pivotal to the formation of the GNU, built on power-sharing arrangements to foster stability through collaboration. However, with the result of 2024 national election, there is a shift in the political landscape of South Africa with multi-party governance to facilitate cooperative and stable governance. Employing qualitative research method and coalition theory, this paper seeks to answer the question of whether the formation of GNU in South Africa is a shift in its political landscape or a relationship of political parties with mutual survival for relevance. The paper concludes that, though South Africa has had to find solutions to several social, economic, and political questions begging for answers in the polity to achieve some degree of national cohesion to mitigate the challenges of inequality, which requires political stability for policy innovation. However, this work believes that most political parties in the GNU are there to punch up their relevance in the polity.

Keywords: Africa, democratic alliance, opposition, provinces, apartheid, freedom

The adoption of an inclusive democratic system in 1994, following the demise of the apartheid system mark the beginning of a political shift in South Africa's political system. Thirty years down the line, there has been some sort of maturity in South Africa's political space. With the entrenchment of a multiparty system, contests for public office have increasingly become highly competitive, coupled with their attendant complexity owing to the increase in the number of political parties and candidates who contest elections. An inclusive democratic system has long been regarded as the best form of government; however, it has revealed its own fundamental flaws. In South Africa's multiparty system, inclusive democracy has functioned in such a way that one [dominant] party secures an absolute majority and governs the country for three decades, while the second-largest party assumes the role of official opposition party (Mafumo, 2024).

However, the outcome of South Africa's 2024 national and provincial elections marked a very important political moment in the country since the dawn of democratic governance. Noutchie (2025) comments that the strength of South Africa's democratic system was put to test for the first time after transitioning to democratic

governance in 1994, where none of the political parties that contested the 2024 election was able to secure an absolute parliamentary majority. The outcome of this electoral shift necessitated the formation of a Government of National Unity (GNU), a political model that reintroduced coalition politics into the South African political landscape, hitherto dominated by a single ruling political party.

The 2024 electoral landscape echoed the high-stakes atmosphere of 1994 (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2024). Further to this, Masuabi (2024) reiterates that the 2024 electoral process was marked by the entrance of new political parties into the polity, significant realignments, and a resurgence of what some have described as Zulu nationalism, which underpinned support for former President Jacob Zuma's MK party. Thus, explaining why, the election was described as a 'watershed' (Rubin & von Soest, 2024). The worsening state of the social, political, and economic conditions in the country and the deteriorating state of very important national infrastructure under the ANC's leadership in the last 30 years of democratic governance were the sources of deep dissatisfaction for the party ahead of the 2024 elections. Hence, the reason for the poor performance of the ANC with 40.18%, which is insufficient for a parliamentary majority, marked the end of its electoral dominance since 1994, thereby making a coalition government inevitable (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2024).

Within the South African historical context vis-à-vis the contemporary, the concept of a GNU in South Africa is not new. The ANC, National Party, and Inkatha Freedom Party were the main parties in the first GNU, which was founded in 1994 under Nelson Mandela and was based on the interim Constitution (Clause, 88). Mandela served as president and de Klerk as deputy president (South

Author Note

Toyin Cotties Adetiba, Department of Political and International Studies, University of Zululand, South Africa
Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0414-9289>
I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Toyin Cotties Adetiba, Department of Political and International Studies, University of Zululand, South Africa
E-mail: adetibat@unizulu.ac.za

African History Online, 2014). Its goals were peace, reconciliation, adoption of a new Constitution, and launching the Truth and Reconciliation Commission. The first GNU was dissolved when the National Party withdrew in 1996, highlighting its fragility and contextual nature. Noutchie (2025) agreed that the first South African coalition government was based on a negotiated transition that was carefully constructed to engender true reconciliation and nation-building. Ragolane and Khoza (2024) and Steytler (2024) however, believe that the new GNU is a product of political expediency, an offshoot of a fragmented political landscape without the benefit of the country's symbolic unity. Ihembe, Isike, and Onwuzuruigbo (2024) further stated that the GNU emerged partly as a mathematical solution to the outcome of the 2024 national election and as a response to the decayed institutional, socio-economic, and pressures from civil society.

It must be clearly stated that although it is politically possible for the new GNU to promote inclusivity in governance and obliterate a drift to authoritarian government, if driven by short-term political survival of the political parties in the GNU, rather than intelligible and articulate planning, it may produce governance paralysis where party differences rule the day. Excluding 42 unrepresented political parties at the regional and provincial levels, the Independent Electoral Commission (2024) reports that 52 political parties registered for the 2024 general elections. Of these political parties ten political parties formed the GNU, these political parties are African National Congress (ANC), Democratic Alliance (DA), Inkatha Freedom Party (IFP), Patriotic Alliance (PA), Good, Pan Africanist Congress of Azania (PAC), Freedom Front Plus (FF+), United Democratic Movement (UDM), Rise Mzansi, and Al Jamaah (Anders, 2024).

Gumedé (2023) and Bosman, Rubidge, and Gruzd (2024) note that South Africa entered the GNU without a well-codified legal framework to guide the formation of and governance in a coalition government. Within the premise of the parliamentary democracies with legal framework mechanisms for the distribution of portfolios and coherent resolution of disputes, South Africa's constitutional architecture provides little or no guidance on power-sharing. Significantly, the success or failure of the GNU in South Africa, especially for other African democracies trying to handle coalition governance and electoral plurality, will have significant implications. Thus, the course of South Africa's coalition experiment will either serve as a cautionary tale about unstructured power-sharing or as a model for adaptation (Obe, 2024). Drawing on recent political developments and scholarly insights, this study evaluates whether the GNU is a shift in South Africa's political landscape or a relationship of political parties with mutual survival for relevance.

Method

Clarified by Makula (2023), the best research method that can be used to explain the phenomena of human interaction, people, actions, and social settings that provide the context for meaning is the qualitative research method. This study involves gathering, analysing, and interpreting secondary data related to the topic. Typically, this method is employed when there is no feasible direct field research but requires a comprehensive synthesis of existing knowledge. Hence, data from journal articles and media reports from South Africa serve as the unit for analysing issues and trends on GNU in South Africa. While this method provides a high-level perspective, it has limitations in comparison to direct fieldwork,

such as reliance on secondary data accuracy and inability to capture real-time dynamics.

Literature and Theoretical Clarification

The adoption of coalition governments is increasingly becoming common worldwide. This is primarily due to shifts in electoral systems, and South Africa is no exception. Thus, the preference for coalition governments over single-party rule can significantly influence the evaluation of new electoral systems (Zweni, Faku, & Yan, 2025). In contemporary African politics, post-election coalitions of political parties are increasingly becoming a significant feature, thus giving us more understanding of election dynamics and formation of government in African politics (Kadima, 2014).

According to Mokgosi, Shai, and Ogunnubi (2017), Political coalitions originate in European countries, such as former East Germany, old Czechoslovakia, Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania and in two of Yugoslavia's six republics. Zweni, Faku, and Yan (2025) added that globally, it has spread to the Nordic countries, the Benelux countries, Brazil, Chile, Australia, Austria, Germany, Greece, Cyprus, East Timor, France, Israel, Italy, Japan, India, Indonesia, Ireland, Kosovo, Latvia, Lebanon, Lithuania, Malaysia, Nepal, and Guinea Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho in Africa.

In Noutchie's (2025) view, the formation of the GNU in South Africa in 2024 arose from a politically incoherent and disjointed political space dictated by the fatigue in its various socio-economic institutions, a decline in South Africans' trust in public institutions, coupled with epileptic, worsening service delivery. Noutchie (2025) further comments that the general elections of 2024 were a significant phenomenon in that it was the final nail on the ANC's underperformance in post-apartheid South Africa's electoral trends, as the incumbent political party (ANC), for the first time, failed to secure a majority since the beginning of inclusive parliamentary democracy in 1994. Thus, reflecting the outcome of the long-term dissatisfaction with unsatisfactory performance of the ANC-led government in the provision of service delivery marred with corruption scandals, and credibility of its members holding portfolios in governance (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2025). Booyesen (2024) concurs that from the first democratic national elections of 1994 to the democratic election of 2024, the South African polity had maintained a de facto system where the ANC had maintained a one-party dominance within a multiparty democracy. A period that accounted for ineffectiveness and lack of accountability in governance.

In any parliamentary democracy, voters are the ones who decide which government or party they want. Debatably, it can be said that South Africans in the general election of 2024 spread their votes to cut across all South African political parties (big or small), hence the reason for which there was no absolute winner in the 2024 general election. According to Mohamed (2024), the political behaviour of South African voters is driven by their distrust of the lack of service delivery, uncontrolled corrupt practices, and empty promises from the ANC. In his analysis, South Africans decided on the Government of National Unity (GNU) by not giving any political party an outright majority of the required 50+1% for a party to form government in South Africa's parliament. As such, political parties that had hitherto been at each other's throat were had no choice but to work together, hence the formation of the current GNU (Mohamed, 2024).

The South African political space in 2024 was overtly or covertly challenged with a visibly electoral outcome that did not go in favour of the incumbent ANC (Mathebula, 2024) and hence political parties were duty-bound to negotiate a power-sharing arrangement. Power sharing is a compromise solution or a politically acceptable agreement between political parties who were presumably in conflict with each other and characterised by different political ideologies. This arrangement resonates with the model of the GNU that was employed during South Africa's transition from apartheid to inclusive democratic governance. Ragolane and Khoza (2024) and Steytler (2024) write that, in contrast to the unifying philosophy and a constitutionally mandated act of transitional reconciliation that incorporated the three largest parties in 1994, the current GNU hatched in 2024 is devoid of a common political vision, it was driven mostly by political expediency. They conclude that the GNU of 1994 was built on the principle of reconciliation and transitional legitimacy, while the current GNU was a child of electoral necessity in a deeply politically fractured society (Ragolane & Khoza, 2024; Steytler, 2024).

Mafumo (2024) and Booysen (2024) writes that following the result of the 2024 general election, considered to be a watershed in South Africa, that saw the ANC losing its hitherto outright majority at the national level and in three of South Africa's nine provinces (Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal, & the Northern Cape), the ANC for obvious reason found itself in the pole position to lead the establishment of the GNU. Hence, the origin of the appellation of the resultant government (Ihembe et al., 2024). Further to this, Ihembe et al. (2024) believe that the concept of the GNU falls within the conceptual bowl of a coalition type referred to as contract parliamentarism with a dose of confidence and supply agreement, concluding that the contract found expression in the statement of intent signed by political parties that agreed to form the GNU. Largely, the coalition government, according to Ihembe et al., is a pedestal to strengthening democratic institutions in South Africa, however, this is subject to the response to the imperative of accountability and responsiveness in governance.

According to Noutchie (2025), several areas of governance that have been experiencing unending political stress would witness a significant relief through the GNU. Naidoo and Levy (2025) and Alexander (2025) added that prominent among these issues is the ideological differences between the two largest coalition partners, the ANC and the DA. This difference bothers on fiscal policy, economic reform, and public spending. For obvious reasons, this has somewhat stalled consensus-building and delayed the execution of important legislative matters.

From the intent of this work, the GNU could present a fundamental shift in South Africa's political landscape; it may prove to be a mere pragmatic alliance driven by political parties' mutual desire for survival and relevance. Therefore, the existence of smaller parties, which frequently act as swing actors, can make the coalition's stability more complex. As a result, they can influence legislative results by strategically aligning with one party or the other, which sometimes shows how unpredictable policy continuity might be under the GNU government (Chikane & Everatt, 2025).

According to Pedersen (2012), the goals of a political party often affect its political behaviour and, hence, party democracy. Very important to every political party is the way they handle the power delegated to them by the voters, they strive to ensure the relevance of their presence in any given government. According to Laver and

Schofield (1990) theories of coalition formation in a multiparty democracy base their assumptions on fundamental expectations about the goals of political parties in the coalition. In essence, there are variations in party goals. Pedersen (2012) thinks that most coalition theories believe that political parties in coalition government fundamentally place importance on goals of votes garnered during election, office, and how they can influence policy based on their influence in the parliament, thus making all the political parties in the coalition seemingly equal but with differences in their goals.

Theoretically, the differences in the goals of political party (ies) means that party behaviour in terms of the formation of a coalition must take into consideration these differences and their causes into account. Through empirical observation, party goal differences means that political parties in a coalition government respond to opportunities and challenges differently. Basically, political parties represent their members and voters differently. Pedersen (2012) further states that the assumption of the early coalition theories is that political parties have one goal, which is to seek votes to get into office, but their primary goal is to obtain office benefits. Hence, Kadima (2014) advances that the formation of a coalition government is a win-lose scenario where cabinet portfolios are the payoffs.

According to Strøm (1990), most political parties have more than one goal. This may be defined by their size and ideology and sometimes may be influenced by the number and size of political parties in the coalition. It therefore means that political parties have more than multiple goals, some of which might be influenced by the political environment, which are often conflicting. Thus, political parties somewhat form alliances not because they are ideologically in tandem, but because it increases their accessibility to achieving their goals while seeking political relevance.

Given the above, Strøm (1990) put forward that three goals are peculiar to political parties: a well-defined policy that could influence public policy, maximising the share of votes earned in an election, and office, conceived as a form of private good allocated to individuals through politically discretionary appointments within the coalition government structure. The fourth, though not considered as visible in policy cycle, is a careful and active representation of party members' wishes (Harmel & Janda, 1994) referred to as intra-party democracy (Pedersen, 2012).

In political science literature, I have not come across a theory that talks to survival for relevance and have thus coined the term "theory of survival for relevance". This suggests that political actors in a coalition government are susceptible to adopt political strategies that are not necessarily meant to achieve social, political, and economic efficiency, but to remain visible, influential, and indispensable within the coalition. It therefore means that survival itself is tied to staying relevant in the eyes of the public or political power holders. Hence, the question of whether the GNU in South Africa is a shift in its political landscape or a relationship of political parties with mutual survival for relevance?

The Nature and Mechanics of the GNU in South Africa

A government of national unity can be conceptualised as a type of broad, multiparty coalition seemingly formed when multiple major political parties, including opposition parties, agree to share power to govern together in the interest of national interests such as nation-building, social order, and peace and stability. It is a coalition that

comprises most political parties and interests represented in the parliament. In other words, the GNU can be described as a government designed to encourage national cohesion and promotion of national unity to avert a return to disorder (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2024). In agreement, Beukes, Chigwata, and de Visser (2024:7) hold that GNUs are generally formed with the principal goal of bringing together shades of different political interests in response to a political crisis.

Usually, this arrangement is adopted in exceptional or political crises, such as times of war or national emergency, which allows the parties involved to present a common front while trying to find a solution to such a crisis. It can also be adopted in a period of political gridlock. This period is characterised by the inability of a single political party to secure the majority during an election for it to form a government. This is the case of the present political space in South Africa. It can also be formed after internecine war or deep political division. This is usually done to promote reconciliation and political stability. For example, following the post-election violence in 2008 in Zimbabwe, Robert Mugabe's ZANU-PF and Morgan Tsvangirai's MDC formed a Government of National Unity to end the crisis (Nhengu & Murairwa, 2020). Bosnia and Herzegovina Government of National Unity framework is another example, the Dayton Peace Agreement (DPA) was signed after a three-and-a-half-year period in December 1995. With this, a government of national unity that brought hope of lasting peace, described as the new 'social contract' that presented the prospect of reconciliation and democracy, was established (Kapic, 2022).

According to Booysen (2011), the GNU in South Africa was conceived to promote inclusivity and national reconciliation under the concept of sunset clauses while considering the country's dark past under the obnoxious apartheid system. The interim constitution of 1994 guaranteed that any political party with 20% seats in parliament and agrees to participate in government is eligible for one or more ministerial appointments. Hence, the first GNU was formed by the National Party (NP), African National Congress (ANC), and Inkatha Freedom Party (IFP) (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2024). Further to this, Booysen (2024), added that the uninterrupted period of three decades that the ANC governed at national level (1994 to 2024), was synonymous with *de facto* ANC one-party dominance within was synonymous with *de facto* ANC one-party dominance within a political system of competitive, multiparty democracy and rooted in constitutionalism. As such, there was no need for a coalition. However, the 2024 national election opened a new political landscape in South Africa.

Considering the role played by the ANC during the dark days of apartheid, Ihembe, Isike and Onwuzuruigbo (2024) point out that because of the support from the majority black South Africans, the party enjoyed some sort of political dominance for as long as support continues. As a result of this, the party became arrogant about its dominance of South Africa's political space, notwithstanding its inability to provide good governance, particularly around service delivery marred by corruption. The former president of the party and the country, Zuma, in 2004, boasted that ANC would remain in power till the second coming of (Setlhalogile, 2024). Metaphorically, it seems the second coming of Jesus has come to pass for the ANC as it can no longer rule without a coalition government after the 2024 elections, as observed by Setlhalogile (2024). Ihembe, Isike, and Onwuzuruigbo (2024) assert that this level of arrogance can be compared to Vincent Ogbulafor [the

Chairman of the People's Democratic Party (PDP) in Nigeria], who conceitedly commented that PDP will govern Nigeria for 60 years. Regrettably, the party's dominance only lasted for fifteen years before it was voted out of power in 2015. The ANC also suffered the same fate when the South African electorate withdrew their support for the party and hence lost the 2024 election. The aftermath of the 2024 election was the formation of the GNU with the aim of achieving national interest, where various political parties and independents operate across the left-right continuum.

Practically, the GNU is aimed at resurrecting the spirit of cooperation and consensus politics of the 1994 GNU. Unlike the 1994 GNU under the Interim Constitution that mandated the inclusion of political parties with 20% or more parliamentary seats in cabinet, the current GNU that emerged in 2024 has no specific constitutional framework. Further to this, the 2024 GNU was formed at a time when the former apartheid enclave was in dire socio-economic circumstances, unlike 1994 when South Africa was just transitioning into inclusive governance, constantly threatened by violence and disorder (Beukes, Chigwata, & de Visser, 2024). Thus, the 2024 GNU's framework was designed to allow key stakeholders from various political backgrounds to share power, thus ensuring that no single entity dominated the initial post-apartheid governance landscape. Fundamentally, this inclusivity was intended to reduce political tensions and instability while crafting a vision for a united South Africa.

The current GNU (officially formed in June 2024) functioned through a power-sharing formula between the political parties that formed the GNU. The ten political parties that formed the GNU are: African National Congress (ANC), Democratic Alliance (DA), Inkatha Freedom Party (IFP), Patriotic Alliance (PA), Good, Pan Africanist Congress of Azania (PAC), Freedom Front Plus (FF+), United Democratic Movement (UDM), Rise Mzansi, and Al Jamaah (Zweni, Faku, & Yan, 2025). Of the 400 seats in the South African National Assembly, the GNU partners control about 70% of the seats. Collectively, these political parties control 287 seats as follows: ANC 159 seats, DA 87 seats, PA 9 seats, Inkatha Freedom Party (IFP) 17 seats, GOOD 1 seat, Pan Africanist Congress of Azania (PAC) 1 seat, Vryheidsfront Plus (FF+) 6 seats, United Democratic Movement (UDM) 3 seats, Rise Mzansi 2 seats, and Al Jama-ah 2 seats (Beukes, Chigwata, & de Visser, 2024).

The GNU's commitment to values like nation-building, social cohesion, togetherness, non-racism, and non-sexism emphasizes its mission to advance collaboration while promoting inclusivity. The GNU aims to unite disparate political parties and work together to realize the goals of South Africa's 1996 Constitution by upholding these ideals. As stated above, the GNU ten political parties operate across the left-right continuum. It is therefore anticipated that within the GNU, there will be inter-party conflicts during the governance cycle. By implication, effective and productive conflict management and balancing diverse social, political, and economic interests of coalition partners will depend on how participating political parties reach a compromise as well as accommodate shades of differences and resolve issues to sustain the coalition government (Beukes, Chigwata, & de Visser, 2024).

As mentioned above, there are no formal legal mechanisms to support the formation of coalition governance. Noutchie (2025:464) puts forward that in political systems that frequently experience coalitions, regulations oversee the allocation of ministerial positions, outline decision-making processes, and set up

mechanisms for resolving disputes. Nevertheless, within South Africa's constitutional structure, there are no explicit guidelines for creating a coalition government. This implies that the 2024 GNU was shaped, formulated, and influenced by party interests rather than being based on institutional design supported by public engagement (Beukes, Chigwata, & de Visser, 2024).

Constituting the cabinet, the GNU adopted what Beukes, Chigwata, and de Visser (2024) and Beukes (2021) called the twinning mechanism, a political arrangement that creates a cross-check on the coalition partners and enhance transparency and accountability and encourages cooperation and collaboration among the coalition partners. The allocation of ministers and deputy ministers was in proportion to performance of the coalition partners in the election of 2024.

Table 1

Distribution of Portfolios among the Coalition Partners of the 2024 GNU

Political Parties	Minister	Deputy Minister
African National Congress	20	33
Democratic Alliance	6	6
Inkatha Freedom Party	2	2
Patriotic Alliance	1	
Good	1	
Pan Africanist Congress of Azania	1	
Freedom Front Plus	1	
United Democratic Movement		1
Rise Mzansi		
Al Jamaah		1

Note. Source: <https://www.sanews.gov.za/special-features-archive/gnu-cabinet-announced>

From the above table, it shows that the ANC is still at the driver's seat of South Africa's political vehicle. The composition of the ministerial positions reflected the ANC's approach to ensure it retained its control of national power. Booysen (2024) however, contends that the numerical representation of political parties in the GNU's cabinet deviated from proportionality while confirming that the ANC is still in charge, notwithstanding its electoral losses. Further to this, of the 10 political parties that formed the GNU, only 9 political parties were included in the executive. As shown in the table, the non-inclusion of Rise Mzansi in the cabinet shows the disproportionality of the GNU's ministerial distribution. According to the table, these ministers are part of the 32-member cabinet or among the 43 deputy ministers.

From the Gamson's Law (Butler, 2024) the key resource political parties possess is the proportion of seats they hold in the legislature, which will closely match the share of ministerial portfolios they secure. In other words, parties making coalition deals expect the payoff from the deal to be proportional to the resources they bring to it. This is, however, different from the South Africa's 2024 GNU. Holding more portfolios than proportional in the GNU shows that the ANC is still the de facto party steering policy direction and implementation. Hence, revealing the ANC's political strategy to ensure its survival, while it raises questions about the durability of the GNU and clarity of purpose.

A Shift in Political Landscape or Survival Strategy?

After winning a 40.18% voter share of the 2024 National election,

the ANC's 30-year electoral dominance of South Africa's political space was over. Notwithstanding, the ANC remains the biggest party in the National Assembly with 159 of 400 seats (Beukes et al., 2024). In relation to the formation of South Africa's first multi-party government at the centre, Malan (2024) comments that the ANC is in a far more powerful position than its electoral performance, thus negating the expected constructive collaboration and partnership. Instead, the ANC had employed a skilful political strategy of duplicity to outwit its opponents. Debatably, the ANC hides under the umbrella of the absence of any legislative or constitutional framework regulating how it should be constituted or run. This brings to the fore the question of whether the adoption of the GNU is a shift in South Africa's political landscape or a survival strategy.

Significantly, South Africa's political space has been influenced by the formation of the GNU, with different political parties coming together to collectively address national issues (Mathebula, 2024). The 2024 national election occurred when South Africa was and still is facing severe social, political, and economic comatose. As a result of citizens' disenchantment with the system, they resort to populist appeal, which has been manifestly demonstrated in South Africa's political space following the emergence of the Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF) in 2013 and the uMkhonto weSizwe Party (MKP) in 2023 ahead of the 2024 national and provincial elections (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2024:163). In the aftermath of the 2024 national elections, South Africa witnessed a significant shift in its political landscape with the formation of the GNU. This marks a complete departure from dominant-party rule toward collaborative, multi-party governance, responding to public desire for cooperative leadership.

Answering a question in a seminar organised by the Department of Political and International Studies, University of Zululand, in March 2025 an ANC member and a deputy minister in the presidency commented that "*South Africans in the election of 2024 have spoken their mind, calling for a collaborative governance, and thus, decided to spread their votes across various political parties in the country. The formation of the GNU is an answer to the question, how can South Africans ensure accountability and good governance in their political system? The GNU has come to stay, and it will be difficult for the ANC and other political parties to sustain their relevance in the South African political space*". Helen Zille of the DA concur that South Africa is in its coalition era and the possibility of a party winning a majority is very slim. This is because political parties do not know what the voters are going to decide, thus an overall majority is rare in a proportional representation system (Haffajee, 2025).

Significantly, the adoption of the GNU in 2024 implies a transformational shift in South Africa's political system. According to Joannou and Coetzee (2009) the ANC had overtly maintained an electoral dominance, following the advent of inclusive democracy in 1994, controlling the state and shaping its national policy with little or no need for consultation from other political parties. However, this political trajectory was disrupted because of the failure of the ANC to secure an outright majority in the 2024 national election. Hence, opting for GNU epitomises a pivotal shift from almost a dominant one-party system towards a coalition model of governance.

Overtly or covertly, this political shift is manifested in several areas of the polity. For 30 years, the political authority was situated within the purview of the ANC, where the social, economic, and

political ship of the country is directed; however, the trajectory has changed, where every decision is subject to negotiation and compromise among the political parties that constitute the GNU (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2024). Corroborating this, Mashamaite and Thusi (2024) and Khambule (2024) confirm that coalition arrangements at the municipal level in South Africa are often born out of electoral necessity rather than common ideology, thus leading to fragile power-sharing and frequent instability over allocation of portfolios and service delivery issues.

Although the ANC remains the biggest party in the National Assembly with 159 of 400 seats, as well as having 20 ministers and 33 deputy ministers [for obvious reasons], institutional arrangements in Parliament and the executive reflects a broader distribution of power, which requires a consensus in decision-making processes (Beukes, Chigwata, & de Visser, 2024). Makhanya (2025) added that the political culture within the polity is also going through a political reconfiguration where citizens, as well as political elites, needless to say, must adjust to the reality of multiparty governance.

What this new political development in South Africa implies is that coalition politics, on one hand, gives room for greater inclusivity, policy moderation, and possible implementation of the principle of checks and balances on executive dominance, which hitherto might not have been possible when it was under one-dominant political party (Zoko, 2025). Given the ideological differences and competing interests among GNU partners, there might be a possibility of policy-making delays (Mashamaite & Thusi, 2024). For instance, disagreements over budgetary allocation and distributions have prompted inquiries into the unity of the coalition (Mathebula, 2024). What this translates to mean is that the GNU is not merely a temporary adjustment/solution to an electoral impasse but a structural shift in South Africa's democratic trajectory, from a majoritarian dominance to a pluralistic power-sharing system which might offer a lifeline to the ANC and the coalition partners (Makhanya, 2025).

Arguably, the ANC, prior to 2024 election, was only doing damage control to its blighted image on account of bad governance. It is evidently clear that South Africa had fared poorly on important indices, such as its inability to deliver development and accountable government, with corruption scandals, erratic power supply, slowed economic growth, deteriorating service delivery, high rates of unemployment, and violent crimes (Ihembe, Isike, & Onwuzuruigbo, 2025). All these put together form the basis of the electorates' discontent with the ANC in the build-up to the 2024 election. It is therefore evident that if the ANC must survive the massive electoral loss of its parliamentary majority in 2024, the party must form a government of national unity. The formation of the GNU makes the most sense for the ANC, which is a means to appease all political players. In other words, the GNU is a lifeline for the ANC, whose loss of majority forced reliance on the coalition to remain in power.

Certainly, the current GNU is not the same as the one set up after the general election of 1994. The 1994 GNU comprised political rivals and was not reliant on other political parties for its survival. Thus, the current GNU lacks the historic purpose of 1994's GNU version, the current GNU appears to have been constructed for political expediency and survival (Mputing, 2024). In other words, the current GNU is vulnerable to collapse if key political parties withdraw, showing that the current coalition is not of strength but of weakness and fragile political deals.

Arguably, one strategy the ANC has been using to maintain its survival within the GNU is through the control of the largest number of cabinet ministers and deputy ministers. To the ANC, this is aimed at maintaining power dynamics within the coalition. According to Beukes, Chigwata, and de Visser (2024), though the GNU includes several parties, the ANC holds a large majority of the cabinet positions. For example, of the 32 ministers, the ANC has 20, and of the 43 deputy ministers, the ANC has 33. Beukes, Chigwata, and de Visser (2024) maintain that in most departments that are politically sensitive or highly visible (e.g., Finance, Trade/Industry, Water & Sanitation, Police, etc.), the ANC ministers were paired with deputies from other parties. Debatably, this arrangement gives the coalition partners a sense of visible involvement and a means to preserve their position within the GNU through the sharing of responsibility to reduce chances of open conflict within the executive.

Within the GNU, the smaller political parties are not left out in the survival struggle. They have been able to exploit the system to their advantage. Notwithstanding their limited electoral support, their endurance within the GNU reflects both institutional and strategic factors embedded in South Africa's political system that ensure inclusivity and coalition bargaining.

Significantly, the outcome of the 2024 general election, which resulted in no single party having an outright majority, heightened the strategic importance of smaller political parties within the GNU. Debatably, these political parties can be regarded as kingmakers in coalition negotiations, leveraging the paucity of parliamentary presence to secure cabinet positions and policy concessions within the GNU (Reuters, 2024). Makwakwa (2025) highlighted that political parties such as GOOD and the Inkatha Freedom Party have been able to exercise some sort of disproportional influence over policy areas, as highlighted in the GNU's Statement of Intent. Thus, allowing smaller parties to remain visible and influential actors in both legislative and executive spaces.

Strategically, smaller political parties in the GNU have been able to sustain themselves by focusing on underrepresented policy domains. Makwakwa (2025) contends that GOOD's emphasis on spatial justice and environmental reform, for example, and the IFP's advocacy for rural and traditional leadership issues, has helped to differentiate them from larger competitors. Thus, helping them to reinforce their relevance within a crowded political field.

Contrary to what these smaller political parties stand to gain, there is possibility of facing resource constraints and risk of ideological dilution because of their participation in coalition governance as they try to balance coalition unity with policy integrity (Dube, 2024). Over time, these compromises may weaken their apparent political identities, which may eventually erode voter confidence. Notwithstanding, their role within the GNU as mediators and policy innovators has significantly contributed to the inclusivity and dynamism of South Africa's evolving democratic order.

Conclusion

The GNU in South Africa can be described as a political strategic initiative put together to stabilize the country following the result of the 2024 national elections, where none of the political parties contesting the election won the [absolute] majority, thus putting the former apartheid enclave in a critical state in the 31 years of its inclusive democratic history. The GNU hinges on emphasizing unity and inclusive governance. Unlike the constitutional formula of

1994, the 2024 GNU operate without a formal institutional framework and functions more as a negotiated coalitional agreement, thus raising questions about its durability and clarity of purpose.

This paper attempts to answer the question of whether the GNU in South Africa is a shift in South Africa's political landscape or a relationship of political parties with mutual survival for relevance. Without any contradiction, the South African general elections of 2024 mark the end of ANC's de facto position in South Africa's political system. The decline in its dominance is pivotal for a coalition government at the national level. Observably, the African National Congress (ANC) is yet to accept the adoption of the GNU as a political shift that has orchestrated a new epoch in South African politics. Thus, political parties involved in the 2024 GNU will continuously monitor their progress among the electorate, while the level of credibility and legitimacy that the involvement in the GNU brings to individual political parties will be interpreted by the citizens alike.

Within the rank and file of the GNU partners, the issue of accountability is fundamental to their survival, though it may also impact the credibility and the purpose for which the GNU was formed. Overtly, every political party in the GNU will have to change their political behaviour to assure the electorate of their commitment to good governance and accountability, while strategically working towards improvement in their performance in the national elections of 2029. In other words, the GNU partners will go to great lengths to demonstrate to the electorate that they can perform better if given the chance.

Certainly, the GNU has helped South Africa to avert an immediate political crisis, but at the same time, it has exposed enduring structural limitations within South Africa's political landscape. This includes deep-rooted, systemic barriers embedded in the country's political institutions, governance frameworks, and socio-economic structures that serve as a clog to effective policy implementation, equitable representation, and social transformation. For example, the dominance of the ANC since 1994 has created a systemic political loyalty that outweighs merit in decision-making and appointments. This is why the ANC has decided to allocate to itself the largest chunk of the ministerial positions in the coalition to keep itself afloat within the GNU.

Strategically, the smaller political parties in the coalition are influential players, frequently influencing the results of parliamentary votes and committee resolutions. Hence, the significance of the GNU is to maintain its stance. To sum up, the GNU in South Africa, though a response to an electoral stalemate, can be described as a litmus test to South Africa's democratic resilience. Thus, South Africa's political leaders must be ready to move beyond short-term stay of the GNU and boldly embrace a longer stay of the GNU with a vision for effective, inclusive governance. Debatably, the success or failure of the GNU is capable of transforming the domestic governance outcomes while influencing broader regional debates on coalition government and power-sharing.

References

- Alexander, W. (n.d.). *A bold move or the end? The DA, the ANC, and the Value Added Tax (VAT) strains on the Government of National Unity*. Friedrich Naumann Foundation for Freedom. Retrieved from <https://www.freiheit.org/liberal-workshop-south-africa/bold-move-or-end-da-anc-and-value-added-tax-vat-strains-government>
- ANC 1912 (2024). *Statement of Intent of the 2024 Government of National Unity*, 14 June 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.anc1912.org.za/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Statement-of-Intent-of-the-2024-Government-of-National-Unity.pdf>
- Anders, T. (2024). *Which parties make up South Africa's unity government?* Reuters. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/which-parties-make-up-south-africasunity-government-2024-06-24/>
- Beukes J. (2021). *Hung councils in South Africa: Law and practice*. Dullah Omar Institute, University of Western Cape: Bellville.
- Beukes, J., Chigwata, T., & de Visser, J. (2024). *Unpacking the 2024 Government of National Unity in South Africa: Challenges, opportunities and lessons for Stable Coalition Governance*. Dullah Omar Institute, University of the Western Cape.
- Booyesen, S. (2024). Accountability and representation in South Africa's 2024 elections: A reshaping of the political landscape. *Journal of African Elections*, 23(2a), 1-22.
- Booyesen, S. (2014). Causes and impact of party alliances and coalitions on the party system and national cohesion in South Africa. *Journal of African Elections*, 13(1), 66-92.
- Butler, A. (2024). *Weighing the DA's slice of the unity government*. Business Day: Retrieved from <https://www.businesslive.co.za/bd/opinion/columnists/2024-07-26-anthony-butler-weighing-the-das-slice-of-the-unity-government/>
- Chikane, R., & Everatt, D. (2025). *The captive democracy of SA's coalition governance*. Wits School of Governance. Retrieved from <https://www.wsg.ac.za/news/captive-democracy-sas-coalition-governance>
- de Swaan, A. (1985). Coalition theory and multi-party systems formal empirical theory and formalizing approach to politics. In H. A.M. Wilke (Ed.), *Coalition formation* (pp. 229-260). Elsevier Science Publishers B.V. (North-Holland).
- Dube Nco (2024). *The challenge of political coalitions: The grand GNU "white lie."* Independent Online (IOL). Retrieved from https://independentonsaturday.co.za/sunday-tribune/opinion/2024-10-27-thechallenge-of-political-coalitions-the-grand-gnu-white-lie/#google_vignette
- Haffajee, F. (2025). *DA ahead of ANC in internal party polls as Zille declares water a top Joburg priority*. Daily Maverick. Retrieved from https://www.dailymaverick.co.za/article/2025-10-01-da-ahead-of-anc-in-internal-party-polls-as-zille-declares-water-a-top-joburg-priority/?utm_source=Sailthru&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=first_thing
- Harmel, R., & Janda, K. (1994). An integrated theory of party goals and party change. *Journal of Theoretical Politics*, 6(3), 259-287.
- Ihembe, M. A., Isike, C., & Onwuzuruiigbo, I. (2024). Coalition or government of national unity? Critical reflections on the 2024 elections in South Africa. *Politikon*, 51(3-4), 163-184.
- Independent Electoral Commission. Political parties' statistics. Retrieved from <https://www.elections.org.za/pw/StatsData/PoliticalPartiesStatistics>
- Joannou, N., & Coetzee, T. (2009). Tendencies of a dominant party system in the Free State legislature (1994-2008). *Journal for Contemporary History*, 34(3), 100-118.
- Kadima, D. (2014). An introduction to the politics of party alliances and coalitions in socially divided society. *Africa. Journal of African Elections*, 13(1), 1-24.
- Kapic, T. (2022). The Dayton peace agreement in Bosnia and Herzegovina and lessons for the design of political institutions for a United Ireland. *Irish Studies in International Affairs*, 33(2), 1-26.
- Keil, S., & Aboultaif, E. W. (2024). Power-sharing in the global South. In E. Wassim, E. W. Aboultaif, S. Keil, and McCulloch (Eds.), *Power-sharing in the global South: Patterns, practices and potentials* (pp. 1-17). Springer Nature.
- Michael, L., & Schofield, N. (1990). *Multiparty government: The politics of coalition in Europe*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Mafumo, T. N. (2024). Uncertainties with the government of national unity in South Africa. *Journal of Public Administration and Development Alternatives*, 9(3), 164-176.
- Makhanya, S. (2025). Nation-building and reconciliation through coalition governance in South Africa: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Business and Social Science Research*, 14(5), 335-347.
- Makula, T. (2023). Independent schools in South Africa: Acculturation of Zimbabwean immigrant teachers. In M. Gutman, W. Jayusi, M. Beck, and Z. Bekerman (Eds.), *To Be a minority teacher in a foreign culture* (pp. 183-199). Springer, Cham.
- Makwakwa, T. (2025). *The real power in the GNU might belong to the smallest parties*. Independent Online (IOL). Retrieved from <https://iol.co.za/news/politics/2025-06-19-the-real-power-in-the-gnu-might-belong-to-the-smallest-parties/>
- Malan, K. (2024). *The GNU order (I): The ANC's partial loss of power*. Politicsweb, Retrieved from <https://www.politicsweb.co.za/opinion/part-i-anc-and-the-south-african-state-in-context->
- Mashamaite, K., & Thusi, M. (2024). Coalition government and service delivery in South Africa: Prospects and challenges for local government. *Journal of Public Administration and Development Alternatives*, 9(1), 92-106.
- Mathebula, B. (2024). South Africa's Government of National Unity: Navigating the Political Landscape. Retrieved from <https://www.knownmagazine.africa/south-africa-government-of-national-unity-navigating-the-political-landscape/>

- Mohamed, S. (2024). Persistent and obscene inequality: A post-apartheid policy choice. *New Agenda. South African Journal of Social and Economic Policy*, 93(1), 17-32.
- Mokgosi, K., Shai, K., & Ogunnubi, O. (2017). Local government coalition in Gauteng Province of South Africa: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Conflict and Social Transformation*, 6(1), 37-57.
- Mputing, A. (2024). *Parliament debates the use of the term government of national unity*. Parliament of the Republic of South Africa. Retrieved from <https://www.parliament.gov.za/news/parliament-debates-use-term-government-national-unity>
- Naidoo, V., & Levy, B. (2025). *South Africa's coalition government is at risk of crumbling: Why collapse would carry a heavy cost*. The Conversation. Retrieved from <https://theconversation.com/south-africas-coalition-government-is-at-risk-of-crumbling-why-collapse-would-carry-a-heavy-cost-254302>
- Nhengu, D., & Murairwa, S. (2020). *The efficacy of governments of national unity in Zimbabwe and Lesotho*. Conflict trends. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/85164162/The_Efficacy_of_governments_of_national_Unity_in_Zimbabwe_and_Lesotho
- Noutchie, S. C. O. (2025). Balancing power and policy: governing South Africa through a fragile national unity coalition. *International Journal of Business Ecosystem and Strategy*, 7(3), 463-470.
- Obe, A. V. (2024). *South Africa's new coalition government heralds change for the region and its leaders*. Chatham House. Retrieved from <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2024/06/south-africas-new-coalition-government-heralds-change-region-and-its-leaders>
- Pedersen, H. H. (2012). What do parties want? Policy versus office. *West European Politics*, 35(4), 896-910.
- Powell, D.M., & Aboultaif, E.W. (2024). Power-sharing and constitutional change in South Africa. In E. Wassim, E.W. Aboultaif, S. Keil, and A. McCulloch (Eds.), *Power-Sharing in the Global South: Patterns, Practices and Potentials*. Springer Nature.
- Aboultaif, E.W., Keil, S., & McCulloch, A. (2024). *Power-sharing in the Global South: Patterns, practices and potentials* (p. 37). Springer Nature. http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-45721-0_3
- Ragolane, M., & Khoza, N. G. (2024). *The role of political compromise in South Africa's Government of National Unity: Balancing competing interests for stability and peacebuilding*. ACCORD. Retrieved from <https://www.accord.org.za/conflict-trends/the-role-of-political-compromise-in-south-africas-government-of-national-unity-balancing-competing-interests-for-stability-and-peacebuilding/>
- Reuters (2024). *South Africa's unity government now has five parties, ANC says*. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/south-africas-unity-government-now-has-five-parties-anc-says-2024-06-17/>
- Rubin, M., & Soest, C. V. (2024). *South Africa's Watershed Election: The Dawn of Coalition Politics*. (GIGA Focus Afrika, 3). Hamburg: German Institute for Global and Area Studies (GIGA) - Leibniz-Institut für Globale und Regionale Studien, Institut für Afrika-Studien. <https://doi.org/10.57671/gfaf-24032>
- Ryan, H. E., & Mazzilli, C. (2023). Twinning and development: A genealogy of depoliticization. *Journal of International Relations and Development*, 26, 433-452. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41268-023-00289->
- Setlhalogile, M. (2024). *The ANC's second coming delivered by a messiah of its making*. Retrieved from <https://www.wsg.ac.za/news/ancs-second-coming-delivered-messiah-its-making>
- South African History Online (2014). *South African Government of National Unity (GNU) 1994-1999*. South African History Online. Retrieved from <https://sahistory.org.za/article/south-african-government-national-unity-gnu-1994-1999>
- Steytler, N. (2024). *South Africa's Government of National Unity: Power sharing in a fractured democracy*. IACL-AIDC Blog. Retrieved from <https://blog-iacl-aidc.org/2024-posts/2024/11/14/south-africas-government-of-national-unity-power-sharing-in-a-fractured-democracy>
- Kaare, S. (1990). A behavioral theory of competitive political parties. *American Journal of Political Science*, 34(2), 565-598.
- Zoko, M. (2025). The impact of coalition politics on governance in South Africa: An analysis of the GNU. *Journal of Ecohumanism*, 5(1), 211-229.
- Zweni, A., Faku E. M., & Yan, B. (2025). The formation of a government of national unity in South Africa: Issues, trends, and prospects. *Journal of Nation-building and Policy Studies*, 9(1), 145-164.

Received January 2, 2026

Revision received January 27, 2026

Accepted January 30, 2026